

Concept of Third Eye in Indian Mythology

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Abstract

Revelation of significance of metopic suture in medical science is a big leap forward. Persistence of that suture gives communication in between Olfactory, Trigeminal and Facial nerves. Olfactory has direct connection to forebrain without the intervention of thalamus. This makes the show of 'rapid fire' so popular in TV where questions are asked and answered in jet speed. In Hindu mythology, the Nasion concept was known and they drew Lord Shiva with a third eye and Yoga practitioners focus their attention to Nasion for better cerebral introspection provided metopic suture persists and previous nerves communicate with each other over there.

Introduction

Metopism is the condition of having a persistent metopic suture, or persistence of the frontal metopic suture in the adult human skull. Metopism is the opposite of craniosynostosis. The main factor of the metopic suture is to increase the volume of the anterior cranial fossa. The frontal bone includes the forehead, and the roofs of the orbits (bony sockets) of the eyes. The frontal bone has vertical portion (squama) and horizontal portion (orbital part). Some adults have a metopic or frontal suture in the vertical portion. In uterine period in right and left half of frontal region of the fetus there is a membrane tissue. On each half a primary ossification center appears about the end of the second month of the fetus. Primary ossification center extends to form the corresponding half of the vertical part (squama) and horizontal part (orbital part) of the frontal bone.

At birth the frontal bone contains two portions, separated by the metopic (frontal) suture. Metopism is the condition of having a persistent metopic suture. Metopic suture is regularly obliterated, except at its lower part, by the eighth year, but infrequently persists throughout life. There is no single proven cause of metopism. The occurrence is from mild to serious

situations. Visional, learning, and behavioral problems may happen in serious metopism. Some don't need any medical treatment. Surgery is a successful approach for those who need it. Treatment teams include: neurosurgeons, plastic surgeons, neurologists, oral and maxillofacial surgeons, audiologists, neuroscience nursing professionals, speech therapists, physical therapists, dentist, otolaryngologists, ophthalmologists, psychiatrists, psychologists and social workers.

The metopic suture is a very characteristic suture found persisting long, even for life in contrast to other cranial bony junctions which fuses early, found in midline in between two halves of squamous part of frontal bone. Its premature closure is a surgical indication for intervention as closure limits the growth of frontal lobe of cerebrum. The metopic suture fuses in midline and makes suture with nasal bones to form Nasion. If looked internally inside cranial cavity lies the horizontally placed perforated bony shelf of cribriform plate of ethmoid bone. The Olfactory nerve reaches this point in the form of tract and bulb to give origin to multiple branches to innervate nasal mucosa. So it may be imagined that if Nasion is not sutured and metopic suture is unfused, there is every chance that

More Information

How to cite this article: Datta A, Datta A. Concept of Third Eye in Indian Mythology. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(4):138-40.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(4).18

Keywords:

Metopic suture, Nasion, Olfactory, Trigeminal, Facial nerves, Third eye of Lord Shiva, Yoga.

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olfactory nerves may be in communication with nerves like Facial and branches of Trigeminal. In the development of face Frontonasal process descends from skull overlying forebrain to face bringing its own innervation vomeronasal organ of Jacobson that stays paramedial till roof of mouth cavity in the vicinity of incisive canal.

Figure 1: Human Brain Seen from Below. Vesalius' Fabrica, 1543. Olfactory Bulbs and Olfactory Tracts

Figure 2: Baby Skull and Metopic (Frontal) Suture

The mesoderm of maxillary process in the development of face contributes to infraorbital cheek supplied by maxillary branch of Trigeminal nerve while supraorbital mesoderm till superior nuchal line is supplied by ophthalmic branch of Trigeminal nerve. Ophthalmic has supratrochlear and supra orbital branches who assemble at Nasion. How come Facial nerve reach on that region? From the vicinity of Hyoid bone a mesoderm derived from second branchial arch known as Platysmal sheath that moves up to cover face,

forehead, scalp and get attached at superior nuchal line. Muscles derived from platysmal sheath are all supplied by facial nerve. So the facial nerve while reaching scalp pass through Nasion and may come into contact with other nerves at Nasion.

Figure 3: Olfactory Bulb: Sagittal Section of the Human Head Showing the Olfactory Bulb

What kind of effects emerge out of this multiple nerve communication is a matter of scientific investigation as Nasion is the site shown in Hindu mythology as a place of 3rd eye to deity of Lord Shiva. Not only that during meditation teacher asks his students to focus attention on Nasion in closed eyes.

Figure 4: The Image of Lord Shiva's Third Eye

Facial Development

In the development of face five primordia is required. Two mandibular, two maxillary and one frontonasal process. The latter one is a mesodermal condensation on cranium overlying forebrain. That descends on face in between two maxillary processes.

After the facial configuration is made up of, the second branchial arch mesenchymal musculature invades face from neck to cover whole face and ascends to scalp till superior nuchal line. This is the muscle of facial expression and supplied by facial nerve while underlying five mesodermal primordia are supplied by Trigeminal nerve.

It is noted interestingly that at the point of Nasion, in an open metopic suture, cranial nerves Olfactory, Trigeminal and Facial communicate.

Functional Interpretation

Face is the mirror of a person's mental status. In a rapid communication, not only verbal interaction take place but a great deal of facial expression matters and that too in rapid succession. How does that work? Right from Optic to Hypoglossal nerves all pass through thalamus where all fibers undergo decussation before normal interactions at nuclear level. It indicates integrations by thalamus between vast character of senses with cortical decisions in background. Response cannot be immediate and instantaneous because fibers pass through many decussations and constitute a final cortical message. But we observe communications like 'rapid fire' where female anchors are quite adept in such performance and asks rapid questions one after another in rapid succession and answers are obtained from interviewees in similar quick manner. So where lies the trick?

First of all, Olfactory is such a nerve who never pass through thalamus. It reports directly to forebrain and gets instant feedback by cortico nuclear fibres connecting facial, vagus and hypoglossal nuclei in brain stem to generate facial expression and vocal response. Secondly, we have to focus on Nasion where connection of Facial nerve with Olfactory and Trigeminal makes the forebrain decision propagated to Facial instantly into expression and at lower medulla to create vocalisation. This phenomenon we see everyday and more practised

in TV serials, debates or meets. But this is not an expression of wisdom unless pre-rehearsed that needs the help of thalamus who in turn gives access to rhinencephalon that stores old memories. Anything in rapid may not always fool proof.

In Hindu mythology while drawing the picture of Lord Shiva the artist always gives a third eye at the point of Nasion that is explained as inner vision and the Yoga practitioners are being taught to focus at Nasion and meditate to sharpen their inner vision.

Conclusion

Implication of split metopic suture has been discovered in Western world and preclosure is dealt surgically. Nasion is the bony junction where open metopic suture gives communication between Olfactory, Trigeminal and Facial nerves. Olfactory has direct connection with forebrain so gives immediate facial expression by virtue with Facial contact. This truth has long been known to Hindu mythologists by depicting a third eye on Nasion at Lord Shiva and focusing attention on Nasion during Yoga practice.

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